

The Bible of AI™ OpenScience

Research programs

The Bible of AI™

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1° Program.- The "Award for most cited publication", incentive to the quality of the publications

Bases: First edition. (July, 15 - 2020)

1. The **total donations** made in this program will make public here by a descriptive annual report.
2. The metrics on our website will be valid identifiers to identify the winner. The metrics are called "**Impact**" in the system, on the "Dashboard" menu up. (The data will be published here).
3. **100%** of the donations obtained (less taxes) in this program, will be allocated to the author/s of the "**Most cited paper published here**", regardless of the areas or topics where it was published, described on the [home page](#) in this website.
4. The award-winning author/s must commit to republishing an **unpublished work** (new publication) **here** in one of the 4 areas: #Society, #Medicine, #Cybersecurity or #Automotive, within a **maximum period of 6 months** after awarding the prize.
5. In case of resigning the first awarded, this will be the second awarded most cited and so on.
6. The name/s of the winner and the total amount of the scholarship awarded will be publicly displayed here: the title of the winning publication and the impact of the collected metrics.
7. **Computable period:** from July 15, 2020 to July 15, 2021.
8. This award will be held annually and will be for a minimum of 5 years from its first edition.
9. A digitally signed and downloadable document in PDF format will be posted on this website, to stamp these terms in content and time before launching the first publication on this site.

2° Program.- The "Research grant", Impulse for researchers to publish

Bases: First edition. (July, 15 - 2020)

1. The **total donations** made in this program will make public here by a descriptive annual report.
2. A **list** of authors and publications will be published here.
3. **75%** of the total donations obtained in this program (less taxes) will go to grant the "**Author/s who has published the most papers here**", in the sum total of the areas and topics described on the [home page](#) in this website.
4. This scholarship must be used to continue publishing new publications (at least one more) **here**, within a **maximum period of 6 months** after awarding the award.
5. In case of resigning the first awarded, this will be the second awarded that has published the most papers and so on.
6. The name/s of the winner and the total amount of the scholarship awarded will be publicly displayed here.

7. **The remaining 25%** of the donations obtained in this program (less taxes) will be used to recruit researcher/s to work on this project (as a precondition they have published in this system previously) to expand and improve the possibilities and objectives that it currently has.
8. **Computable period:** from July 15, 2020 to July 15, 2021.
9. This award will be held annually and will be for a minimum of 5 years from its first edition.
10. A digitally signed and downloadable document in PDF format will be posted on this website, to stamp these terms in content and time before launching the first publication on this site.
- 11.

Bodies responsible for the management and control of research programs

- The control, accounting and management of the donations and award will be managed by the **Asociación Profesional de Formación y Empleo**, ID: ESG73386724, next to the rules from the future [open call Committee Board](#).
- **These two institutions** will present public acts signed by their managers of all the donations and winners and the content described in the previous programs. With sufficient legal validity.

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